

Fables from Panchatantra: A Management Perspective.

Dr. Shivangkumar Maheta ¹, Dr. Krishna Desai ²

¹ Central Library, Vanita Vishram Women's University

² Department of Accountancy, JDSCM, VVWU

¹ Shiv13mehta@gmail.com , ² krishna.desai@vwwusurat.ac.in

Abstract:

Fables of Panchatantra is a very well-known collection of stories with moral lessons. It has attracted readers despite of their age and religious background, not only in India but whole world wide. One of the reasons for its popularity is attributed to the fact that the story personifies birds and animals having human vices and virtues and thus, gives lessons on righteousness and conduct in life. It is "certainly the most frequently translated literary product of India" and these stories are among the most widely known in the world for its preachings and wisdom.

This paper attempts to reiterate five famous fables from the collection of 87 stories in context of the process (functions) of management and also extract important management fundas from it. It is an attempt to establish a bridge between the ancient Indian wisdom and the modern management concepts. It also highlights the obvious moral and ethical lesson from these stories. These lessons are stepping stone for a strong character building of modern managers since, ultimately, it is the moral character of the management personnels that is reflected in a transparent undertakings of an ethical business entity.

As laid down in the National Education Policy – 2020, it is utmost important to explore the indigenous knowledge of ancient India and establish its relevance in present time so that our offsprings and generation to come takes pride in our cultural heritage and tradition. It also shall be helpful in developing innovative teaching pedagogy, specially to management students.

Key Words:

Panchatantra, Management Process, Management Lessons, IKS, Panchatantra Tales, Moral Education

Introduction to Panchatantra:

According to Wikipedia, The Panchatantra is an ancient Indian collection of interrelated animal fables in Sanskrit verse and prose, arranged within a frame story. The surviving work is dated to about 200 BCE, but the fables are likely to be much more ancient. The original author of this text is still unknown, but it has been attributed to Vishnu Sharma in some recensions and Vasubhaga in others. The word Panchatantra literally means five (panch) systems (tantra) of Nitishashtra (Science of Wise Conduct). It attempts to teach us, how to understand people, how to choose reliable and trustworthy friends, how to meet difficulties and how to problems through tact and wisdom, and how to live in peace and harmony amidst deceit, hypocrisy and other pitfalls in life. In fact, it is a novel way to impart worldly wisdom using the art of storytelling.

According to one of the recensions, The Panchatantra is woven round the frame of a tale of a king who entrusts his three 'dud' sons to a learned man, a Brahmin, called Pandit Vishnu Sharma, to enlighten their minds within six months. The tale is narrated in prose while the exposition of a philosophical and moral theme is put in verse; maxims or wise sayings are also expressed in verse, which either sums up the narration or introduces the next tale. As one fable follows another, people and animals are constantly changing places, and they share the same characteristics of love and hatred, compassion and wit, selfless courage and base cowardice, generosity and meanness. Each story has a moral and philosophical theme which has stood the test of time and so is true even in modern times

Modern Academia ardently supports this way of teaching. If the modern management lessons are taught through such ancient treatise, it will not only lead to innovative teaching pedagogy but also integrate ancient knowledge in today's education system. The New Education Policy 2020 warrants for the same as well. It is believed that Panchatantra supposedly was narrated by the composer, to three princes of a king; to impart them with the wisdom to perform their duties in a morally and politically accurate manner.

The stories in Panchatantra are divided into five different heads. Each category consists of certain number of tales and fables through which morals are taught. Panchatantra stories are categorized as under:

- 1. Mitra Bhedha – Loss of Friends:** Under this head, through different stories and situations, the narrator teaches to avoid unwarranted fights and differences for living a peaceful life. In modern context, it teaches the managers to avoid rift with colleagues, associates, clients and other professional contacts as this can lead to unpleasant consequences like loss of business.

- 2. Mitra Samprapti – Gain of Friends:** Here, the narrator has included the tales that teaches about developing kinship or friendships for mutual benefits and lay emphasis on developing and maintaining relationships. In today's parlance it can be equated with making strategic alliances, team-building, professional associations and trade bodies.
- 3. Kakolukiyam – Crows and Owls (in context of War and Peace):** This head comprises tales on the theme of War and Peace where stories are centred round the theme of being observant, recognizing friends, identifying rivals and being ready to face deceit at the hands of friends and also not under estimating the rivals. Stories under this head teaches corporate lessons of Critical Thinking, Strategic Planning, Behavioural Studies, Crisis Management, Conflict Management and Leadership to modern managers.
- 4. Labdha Prasanam – Forfeit of Gains (in context of losing what is achieved):** The lores included in this section are towards moral education. They emphasis on righteousness and ethical conduct in life. It is relevant to manages for learning lessons of Types of Leadership, Business Ethics and Decision Making.
- 5. Aparikshit Karakam – Inconsiderate Action (in context of good governance):** This is the last head under which stories elucidate characteristics of a good human being and expected framework within which one should live one's life. Modern managers can learn about the leadership development, characteristics of a good leader, professional behaviour and strategic leadership from these bunch of stories.

Introduction to Management and Functions / Process of Management:

Management is the process of planning and organising the resources, operations and workflow of a business to achieve specific goals in the most effective and efficient manner possible. Efficiency in management refers to the completion of tasks correctly and at minimal costs. Effectiveness in management relates to the completion of tasks within specific timelines to yield tangible results.

Management Process refers to series of activities and functions that are performed effectively to achieve the desired goal efficiently. It includes number of interrelated functions like planning, organizing, directing (leading) and controlling.

Management process can be defined as a systematic approach that may be undertaken by the managers to Plan, Organize, Lead and Control business activities resulting into achievement of the object of profit maximization or wealth maximization. It is multi-faceted in nature. Each of the function described above involves a lot of thought before it is implemented.

Planning: Planning involves preparing an action plan to be executed to achieve a goal or complete the work. It serves as a road map to be followed to complete the desired work within a desired time frame. It is one of the most crucial functions of management and it is aptly said the failing to plan is planning to fail. The process of planning tends to answer questions like – what is to be done; where it is to be done, when it is to be done, who has to do it and how it is to be done. Planning aspect of management mostly deals with determination of Vision & Mission Statements, Strategy Building and Establishing Goals and Objectives. Usually, the planning process includes following activities undertaken by managers:

1. Setting Objectives
2. Developing Planning premises
3. Identifying Alternative courses of Actions
4. Evaluating all the identified courses of actions
5. Selecting the best Alternative
6. Implementing the Plan
7. Taking regular follow ups to see if the desired result is obtained.

Organising: The concept of organizing, which refers to the process of arranging resources, tasks, and people in a way that enables an organization to function efficiently and effectively. This includes setting clear goals, structuring roles, delegating tasks, and ensuring cooperation. It is one of the toughest functions of management. Organizing function of management deals with developing Organization Design, Culture and Social Networks. Following steps become necessary for undertaking the function of Organizing by managers:

1. Identifying the work
2. Grouping the work / workers
3. Establishing hierarchy
4. Delegation of Authority
5. Coordination

Directing (Leading): Directing indicates giving guidance or mentorship which is significant to ensure the best use of the available human resources. It necessarily involves managers assuming leadership roles and use various theories of motivation to get the work done. It is a managerial function, around which all other functions revolve. It entails monitoring, motivation, leadership, and communication to ensure that everyone is working efficiently towards the achievement of shared objectives. Four pillars of efficient directing are as under:

1. Leadership
2. Motivation
3. Supervision
4. Communication

Controlling: Controlling refers to taking corrective actions for the implemented course of action through regular follow-up and feedback. It involves preparation of a good control system and having critical thinking to aptly and timely take charge of the situation that is getting beyond the expectation or deviating from the desired action. Controlling as a management function ensures that right things happen, in the right ways and at the right time. Without effective control, direction is lost. It keeps the management process dynamic and grounded. It includes – management by exception, change management, risk management, conflict management, etc. The broad framework of controlling entails following:

1. Development of Systems and Processes
2. Strategic Human Resources Management

Gist of the selected tales of Panchatantra and corresponding Management Lesson:

The Lion and the Rabbit

In this tale, a mighty lion has been terrorizing all the animals in the forest. To protect themselves, the animals come up with a plan to offer one animal each day as its prey. When it is the turn of a clever rabbit, it comes up with a plan to outwit the lion. The rabbit goes to the lion, claiming that it was delayed because another lion claimed to be the king of the jungle. The lion, enraged, demands to see this other lion. The rabbit leads the lion to a well, where the lion sees his own reflection and, thinking it is another lion, jumps into the well and drowns.

Moral Lesson: "Intelligence and Wisdom are far more effective than brawn and brute force."

Management Lessons:

1. **Planning:** A strategy that managers may apply for assessing the opportunities, risks, weaknesses, and strengths of a challenge or an opponent is strategic planning. This aids in figuring out the most appropriate course of action. Even managers can use strategic planning and decision-making to pave the way to success, much like the Rabbit in the fable devise a plan to trick formidable foe – the lion. It's crucial for the managers to acknowledge the

opponent's strengths and weigh the risks involved, but it's even more crucial to spot their weaknesses and exploit them to our advantage.

2. **Organizing:** Managers must arrange their resources and use them wisely to reduce their loss, just as every animal in the wild chose to willingly send one victim to a lion every day. It is crucial to comprehend that where risks cannot be eliminated, the efforts must be towards abating the same. Exactly the way all the animals coordinated within themselves; Cooperation, team-work and collaboration must be used by managers for efficient organizing of business activities. This ensures optimality in all business processes.
3. **Directing / Leading:** Rabbit assumed the leadership role and saved life of all the animals with his wisdom. Similarly, managers must develop peripheral vision for problem solving with their intellect and creative thinking. Communication is one of the important aspects of leading. Rabbit used his communication / persuasion skill to outwit the mighty lion. Effective leaders and managers must develop good communication skill should be able to influence others to achieve desired outcomes. Maintaining composure in adversity, overcoming fear with confidence and intellect, stress management, risk management, innovative thinking are some of the desired qualities of a good leader which are impersonated in rabbit.
4. **Controlling:** Just like rabbit taking control of the situation decided to deal it with the available limited resources – time and wit, managers also must know the knack of using the available resources judiciously. They should ensure that their planned actions are implemented through appropriate control management systems without any deviations.
5. **Leadership Traits:** In this story, the lion's personality represents some of the qualities that leaders and managers should absolutely avoid. As the fierce king of the jungle, the lion chose to depend on the food supplied by other animals, which made him sluggish and also diverted him from his primary skill of hunting. In addition to losing his ability to detect danger, he also underestimated other animals, took pride in vanity, and became over confident which cost him his life. Leaders must always try to sharpen their skills, develop core competence and bring innovative changes to ensure that the business as well they both progress simultaneously.

The Three Fishes

In this tale, three fishes live in a pond. One of the fishes is wise, the second one is average, and the third one is careless. When they overhear a fisherman talking about coming to catch fish, the wise fish immediately plans to swim to a different pond and also requests the other two to

take immediate action. The second fish thinks of staying hidden as it is too confident on its ability to swim deep and decides not to act upon the threat and the third fish, not taking the threat seriously, stays in the pond. The wise fish survives since it successfully shifts, while the other two are caught by the fisherman and dies.

Moral Lesson: “One who acts promptly upon smelling a danger persists.”

Management Lessons:

1. **Planning:** This tale effectively illustrates the value of planning. In an emergency, a well-thought-out plan may prove to be the key to success. A well-considered or planned move can prove to be economically beneficial to the manager, just as the ingenious fish in this fable swam its way back to another pond before the fisherman strikes proved to be a lifesaver for it and its family. In order to keep ahead of his rivals or competitors, a manager must plan his future course of action well in advance. In addition to this, it is crucial to consider all the probable alternatives before making a decision. The scientific planning technique can be used to accomplish this.
2. **Controlling:** The clever fish was able to save its life only because it got successful in controlling the situation. It accurately identified the threat and made the quick decision to move to a safer area. To efficiently handle a crisis with minimal harm, managers should develop their critical thinking and decision-making skills, just like this wise fish. Making an intelligent choice and taking charge of the management problem are vitally important. As was the case with the second and third fishes, it is often gets too late to come out of the problem if we wait until it strikes. Therefore, it's critical to be proactive and react quickly to change.

The Elephant and the Sparrow

This story is about a sparrow who seeks revenge on an elephant that destroyed her nest and killed her eggs: Two sparrows lived in a nest in a banyan tree. One day, an elephant came to the tree to find shade from the sun. The elephant tore off a branch of the tree, which caused the sparrow's eggs to fall and break. The mother sparrow and her friends, including a woodpecker, fly, and frog, planned to get revenge on the elephant. The fly lured elephant into his comfort zone, woodpecker taking advantage of the same, injured his eyes, frog led the thirsty elephant to a marshy area to find water, where the elephant fell into a ditch and died.

Moral Lesson: “A friend in need is a friend indeed.”

Management Lessons:

- 1. Planning:** In this tale, we learnt how a sparrow, woodpecker, a fly and a frog made a plan to avenge the loss of sparrow and kill the elephant. In similar lines, managers must plan their actions to out-wit their competitors. A well devised and executed plan helps in achieving desired goals within the limited time span. A good plan serves as a roadmap to success for any business entity.
- 2. Organizing:** Sparrow, fly, woodpecker and frog came together formed a team, each of them was assigned a specific role, the entire plan was coordinated and implemented by them cohesively and this led to the fall of elephant into the ditch. Managers have to be competent at organizing the resources, identifying the potential of each team member and accordingly divides the work amongst them. Organizing function of management is all about team-work, role assignment, coordination, implementation and staying well connected.

The Bharunda bird

The bharunda is a mythical, two-headed bird, it lives along the Cauvery River. On a day, one head finds a golden fruit and eats it immediately without sharing it with the other head who also was excited to taste it. He told the first head that since he found the fruit, he only will savour it. Next day, the second head finds another new fruit. The first head discourages its consumption, but since, it wanted to even the score for the earlier events, it immediately consumed it and eventually both the heads die.

Management Lesson: “Forgiveness does not alter the past, but it does expand the future.”

Management Lessons:

- 1. Planning:** Planning is evaluating each of the options in front of a management critically and selecting the best plan of action for the future based on the results. Making quick decisions without carefully considering the consequences can backfire on the company. In this story, the two-headed bird consumed the poisoned fruit and perished without considering the consequences of its actions. To prevent needless losses, managers should consider the pros and cons of their decisions. Similarly, the resources should be shared within the organization in a just manner to avoid unnecessary conflicts.

2. **Unity of Command & Unity of Direction (Organizing):** This anecdote is a classic illustration of the kind of calamity that can occur when different persons in the organization have varying levels of command and direction. The organizational structure should have a distinct hierarchy, and ideally, there should only be one supervisor or reporting authority. In the event that there are more, their orders ought to be coordinated with the organization's goals. Henry Fayol promoted both of these contemporary management ideas. Similar to the two-headed bird, the organization likely to lose if it does not comprehend this strategic choice. The bird eventually perished as a result of needless, unhealthy internal competition brought on by the two heads' discord.
3. **Conflict Management (Control):** The entire organization is at risk if internal dispute is not resolved promptly. Internal disputes may cause rash decisions that could end up being harmful to the organization. In this tale, the second head eats the fruit mindlessly in an attempt to win the battle with the first head out of rage and ultimately perishes. There is also an alternate interpretation to the story in terms of conflict management. Every organization has a single "stomach," and its employees are its many heads, or brains, each of whom contributes to the company's overall success. It becomes a surefire prescription for disaster for the entire institution if one, a few, or even many people band together as manipulative persons to pursue their own selfish or egotistical goals. And such a group of people ought to be recognized and dealt with promptly.

Friends to the rescue

This tale is about a deer who is trapped and saved by its friends. A crow, a mouse, a deer and a tortoise are friends living in a jungle. One day, while they were chilling out together, they see a hunter approaching in their direction. Instantaneously, the deer run in to thick forest, mouse hides into a burrow and crow flies away. Unable to move fast, the tortoise is unfortunately caught by hunter. His friends decide to rescue him from the clutches of the hunter. They execute a plan wherein; deer deliberately attracts the hunter to run behind it. Meanwhile, the crow pecks the hunter to distract him from his catch and meanwhile, the mouse using its sharp teeth frees the tortoise who immediately runs back to the lake before the hunter could get his composure back.

Moral Lesson: "Unity is strength. Great things can be accomplished through teamwork and collaboration."

Management Lessons:

1. **Planning:** In this narrative, we observed how the deer, crow, and mouse hatched an intelligent strategy to rescue their comrade the tortoise. They aptly implemented the 4W2H planning premises concept. Modern managers, through this narrative, can comprehend the significance of prompt planning and meticulous execution, which are essential for success. The hunter's personality in this tale also teaches us the significance of making measured decisions rather than falling for too good to be true lures. Before rushing to any higher rewards, managers must take a moment to think.
2. **Organizing:** This story is a wonderful case study to understand more about ability to organize. The crow, deer, and mouse illustrate strategic alliance, cooperation, coordination, and work distribution, presenting a precedent for modern managers for tackling these challenges prudently. When the right employee gets assigned to the right job, productivity increases and work is completed with no collateral damage or cost.
3. **Networking:** Tortoise, though small and insignificant in compared to the agile deer, crow, and mouse, extends a friendly hand to them. All of the creatures in this story belong to different groups of animals in the animal kingdom, but they all hang out together. These examples demonstrate the value of networking and diversity in a team. In difficult times, a strong network might come in handy. Similarly, when people with different skills collaborate in a team, each person's primary competency becomes an advantage. Success happens when each one plays to his or her abilities; strength-based management does work in reality.

Observation: Panchatantra Stories can be considered as a treasure trove for teaching and learning management tactics. Many of the anecdotes in this classic are good case studies for studying modern management concepts. Modern managers may employ the lessons they've learned to manage their businesses with greater effectiveness. This article provides managerial lessons based on chosen Panchatantra stories only. But, a thorough examination of all the stories may offer multiple aspects of modern management frameworks in an easy approach. The table underneath highlights a few crucial rules of management that can be drawn from a particular tale of Panchatantra:

Table 1 Management Lessons from Panchatantra Stories

Sr. No.	Title of the Story	Management Lesson
1	The Monkey and the Wedge	Risk Analysis and Strategic Planning
2	The Jackal and the Drum	Decision Making through Risk Evaluation
3	The Fall and Rise of a Merchant	Organizational Behaviour and Establishing kinship with peers / team-members
4	The Sage and the Jackal	Leadership Qualities – Developing Vigilance and Identifying hidden motives of the opponent.
5	The Cobra and The Crow	Strategic Planning, Critical Thinking
6	The Crane and the Crab	Importance of Planning, Leadership Qualities - Emotional Intelligence, Crisis Management, Out-of-the-box Thinking
7	The Bug and The Flea	Leadership Qualities – Trust Management, Theory of Trust
8	The Blue Jackal	Authenticity in Leadership, Organizational Image, Team Dynamics and Inclusion, Communication Management
9	The Lion, The Camel, The Jackal and the Crow	Leadership Qualities – Trust Management, Personnel Management, Disadvantages of Favouritism at Workplace, Team Dynamics: Equality & Diversity in Team
10	The Birds and The Sea	Leadership Qualities – Perseverance and Planning before Action, Competitor Analysis and Management.
11	The Story of The Tortoise who fell off the stick	Sticking to the course of action that is planned, Leadership Qualities – Focus, Self Control, Team Building and Coordination
12	Damanaka and Pingalaka	Crisis Management, Decision Making and Importance of Planning
13	The Lion and The Jackal	Critical Thinking and Strategic Planning

14	The Monkey and The Suchimukha Bird	Importance of Planning, Disaster Management, Leadership Qualities – Self Control
15	The Bird and the group of Monkeys	Planning Leadership Qualities – Proactivist, Risk Assessment
16	The Story of Dharmabuddhi and Papabuddhi	Code of Conduct for Professionals, Business Ethics, Public Relationship Management
17	The Crane and The Mongoose	Planning: Considering all pros and cons before choosing the course of action, Critical Thinking and Problem Solving
18	The Merchant's Son	Leadership Quality – Determination, Honesty and Nobility
19	The King and The Monkey	Strategic Alliance, Team Building, Coordination, Planned Action, Conflict Management
20	The Thief and The Brahmin	Leadership Quality – Confidence, Self-Awareness and Risk Assessment and Identification
21	The Crow, The Hunter and The King of Doves	Importance of Unity and Harmony in an Organization, Co-ordination and Team Management,
22	The Hermit and The Mouse	Importance of SWOT Analysis before Planning; Strategic Planning
23	Shandili and The Sesame Seeds	Decision Making, Importance of Planning
24	The Merchant's Son	Human Resources Management, Team Building and Conflict Management
25	The Unlucky Weaver Somilaka	Importance of Building Professional Attitude, Organizational Behaviour
26	The Enmity between Owls and Crows	Assessment of Risk, Team Building, Strategic Planning (Strategic Alliances), Adaptation to Change (Change Management)
27	Elephants and Hares	Importance of Communication Skill for managers
28	The Cat, The Hare and The Partridge	Conflict Resolution and Management

29	The Brahmin and The Crooks	Leadership Qualities – Confidence, Common Sense and Clarity of Thoughts.
30	The Brahmin and The Cobra	Risk Assessment and Management, Leadership Qualities – Confidence
31	The Dove and The Hunter	Goal Setting, Leadership, Coordination and Team Building
32	The Old Man, His Young Wife and The Thief	Leadership Qualities – Strategic Pursuit, Keen Observation
33	The Brahmin, The Thief and The Rakshasha	Conflict Management, Leadership Quality - Mindfulness
34	The Tale of Two Snakes	Strategic Planning, Risk Management
35	The Female Mouse	Leadership Qualities – Humble and staying grounded
36	The Tale of The Golden Droppings	Importance of Team Building, Human Resources
37	The Lion, The jackal and The Cave	Risk Assessment and Risk Management, Importance of SWOT Analysis before taking any actions.
38	The Frogs and The Black Snake	Managing Competitors and Avoiding unnecessary rivalry
39	The Crocodile and The Monkey	Crisis Management, Critical Thinking, Culture and Attitude, Critical Thinking, Sales Management
40	The Greedy Cobra and The King of Frogs	Managing Competitors, Risk Management
41	The Lion and The Foolish Donkey	Critical Thinking, Leadership Qualities – Out of the box thinking, Innovative Idea, Behaviour Management
42	The Story of The Potter called Yudhisthira	Planning and Strategic Planning
43	The Lioness and The Jackal	Risk Management
44	Nanda and Vararuchi	Leadership Quality – Forgiveness and Comradeship

45	The Donkey and The Washerman	Human Resource Management, Division of Labour
46	The Farmer's Wife	Business and Moral Ethics, Organizing
47	The Camel with a Bell round his neck	Importance of Planning and Organizing before any action
48	The Jackal, The Lion, The Leopard and The Tiger	Strategic Management, Crisis Management
49	The Dog in a foreign country	Business Environment
50	The Greedy Barber and The Jain Monks	Importance of Research in Decision-making
51	The Brahmin's Wife and The Mongoose	Planning
52	The Story of Chakradhara	Leadership Quality – Application of Knowledge
53	The Lion that sprang to life because of Brahmins	Risk Management, Planning, Resources Management
54	The Four Learned Fools	Leadership Qualities – Common Sense and Mindfulness
55	Two Fishes and The Frog	Risk Management
56	The Story of a Singing Donkey	Time Management
57	The Story of The Weaver	Controlling
58	The Miserly Father	Leadership Qualities – Willpower, Determination
59	The King Chandra	Out of the Box Thinking, Leadership Qualities – Righteous Actions

Conclusion:

The Panchatantra offers ageless knowledge that addresses many aspects of management when viewed through the lens of Indian knowledge systems. The lessons of resource management, teamwork, flexibility, ethical leadership, and strategic thinking are just as relevant now as they were thousands of years ago. Just as the characters in these old fables use their knowledge to solve problems, succeed, and have a positive impact on society while abiding by Indian philosophical ethical norms, one can guarantee the success of their teams and organizations—whether they are multinational corporations or educational institutions—by concentrating on strategic planning, efficient organization, effective direction, and continuous control.

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